

2. Exposure of 0.005% ready-to-use brodifacoum wax blocks at different weeks after transplanting. Arrows indicate time of poison baiting. Treatment at a) 4 WT, b) 6 WT, c) 8 WT, d) 10 WT, e) 12 WT, f) multiple baiting, g) activity in reference fields.

transplanting (WT) with 0.005% brodifacoum bait or 0.005% ready-to-use brodifacoum wax blocks resulted in maximum kill and 70-80% reduction in preharvest tiller cut damage (Fig. 1, 2). Poison baiting at 4 WT or 6 WT with either anticoagulant also was effective in killing rodents.

A large-scale immigration of rodents from surrounding areas near crop maturity resulted in high preharvest tiller damage. Treatment at 12 WT was not effective. Intake of poison bait declined significantly because of the availability of maturing rice grains.

Multiple poison baiting of rodents

with 0.005% brodifacoum or 0.005% brodifacoum baits at 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 WT was most effective in killing existing and immigrating rodent populations.

Bamboo bait stations were used for poison baiting during rainy days. Early consumption of 0.005% brodifacoum bait from these bamboo bait stations was substantial, resulting in high decline in rodent populations, but consumption declined considerably 10 WT. □

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Grain loss due to rat damage

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Of the known pests, the field rat *Bandicota bengalensis* causes substantial losses to the rice crop from sowing to harvest in Haryana.

We surveyed 171 fields in 11 villages of 4 blocks of Kurukshetra district, where mainly Jaya, PR106, and IR8 varieties are grown, from August to harvest in 1984. Maximum damage occurred at tillering and heading stages; tillers were cut 10-15 cm from the ground. The number of rat burrows varied from 2 to 13/field (0.4 ha), and they were confined to field boundaries. Cut tillers were found 5-15 m away from the burrows.

From field samples, we assessed yield losses caused by rats by taking the yield corresponding to the number of cut tillers/m² and the yield of healthy tillers/m². Cut tillers/m² varied from 5.2 to 47.5, grain yield losses ranged from 33.8 to 308.8 g/m². That can be estimated as 0.4 to 3.1 t/ha for Jaya, 0.6 to 1.9 t/ha for PR106, and 0.4 t/ha for IR8 (see table). Rats showed no varietal preference. The yield loss differences among varieties may be due to variations in size of the rat population in different villages. □

Grain yield losses due to rats at Kurukshetra, India, 1984.

Block	Village	Fields observed (no./village)	Variety	Av cut tillers/m ²	Grain loss (g/m ²)	Yield loss (t/ha)
Thanesar	Shadipur	25	Jaya	47.5	308.8	3.1
	Kanipla	15	Jaya	34.5	224.1	2.2
	Kanpur	18	PR106	28.6	185.7	1.9
	Hinga Kheri	11	PR106	13.2	87.8	0.9
Shahabad	Kalsani	16	PR106	8.7	56.6	0.6
	Nagla	13	Jaya	18.0	117.0	1.2
Pehowa	Sandhali	10	IR8	5.2	33.8	0.4
	Saina Saida	15	PR106	12.5	81.2	0.8
	Gumthala	22	Jaya	30.2	196.0	2.0
Cheeka	Sonthi	14	Jaya	6.4	41.3	0.4
	Kakkahri	12	Jaya	8.0	52.0	0.5

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Water management

Supplementary irrigation of upland crops following rice

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We studied the supplementary irrigation requirement of rabi pulses and oil seeds

grown in residual moisture following rice on slightly sloping land.

Crops were sown on 16 Dec 1985. Mungbean was harvested on 18 Mar, urdbean on 25 Mar, and peanut on 1 Apr 1986. A total 77.4 mm of rainfall was received during crop growth. The groundwater table remained at about 80 cm depth (78-83 cm) during the cropping season.

Peanut performed best under residual moisture without irrigation, yielding about 0.7 t/ha (Table 1). One irrigation at flowering almost doubled peanut

yield to 1.4 t/ha. Further irrigation did not result in any significant increase in yield.

Total supplementary water used was 77.4, 127.4, 177.4, and 227.4 mm in the treatments of no irrigation, 1 irrigation, 2 irrigations, and 3 irrigations, respectively (Table 2). □

Table 1. Grain yield of crops following rice under different moisture regimes. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Peanut	Mungbean	Urdbean	Mean
Residual moisture	0.71	0.11	0.15	0.32
Irrigation at flowering	1.36	0.10	0.18	0.54
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation	1.28	0.12	0.19	0.53
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation + pod elongation	1.36	0.18	0.17	0.54
Mean	1.18	0.09	0.17	—
LSD (0.05) for moisture regimes for crops				0.08
for 2 crops under Same moisture regime				0.11
for 2 moisture regimes for same crop or different crops				0.22
				0.18

Table 2. Irrigation requirement under different moisture regimes. New Delhi, India.

Treatment	Irrigations (no.)	Water applied (mm)		Total water needed (mm) including rainfall
		Irrigation	Rainfall	
Residual moisture	0	0	77.4	77.4
Irrigation at flowering	1	50	77.4	127.4
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation	2	100	77.4	177.4
Irrigation at flowering + pod initiation + pod elongation	3	150	77.4	227.4

Effect of water regime on yield and water use of rice

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We studied the effect of three water regimes on yield and water used for evapotranspiration (ET) during 1985 kharif (Jun-Oct) at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° 3' E). Treatments were continuous submergence of 5±1 cm and static water tables at 30 cm and 60 cm depths below soil surface.

The experiment was carried out in 3 replications in field-installed RCC tank lysimeters 1.8 × 1.5 m area and 1.5 m depth filled with Beni silty clay loam series (Mollisol) soil of Pantnagar. Soil had 9% sand, 61% silt, and 30% clay; pH 6.3; cation exchange capacity 20.0 meq/100 g; bulk density 1.33 g/cm³; 3.4% organic matter; retained 34.6% moisture at 1/3 bar and 11% at 15-bar tension; and hydraulic conductivity of 0.82 cm/h. ET was calculated from daily change in water table (considering soil